

Rural household head employment status and remittance inflows from Italy

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ABSTRACT

This paper analysed the effect of the employment status of household head amongst 10 villages on the remittance determinants of remittance receiving households in rural Bangladesh from Italy. Using micro-economic data from a survey conducted in 2013, multivariate analysis was carried out on 300 rural households. The empirical findings provided that the differences of the relationship among the other three (housewife, businessman and other) employment status of the household head. As for housewife is mostly associates with the age of migrant, marital status of the migrant, number of visit by the migrant, age of household head, investment in housing development and household living expenses. While businessman is closely related with all variables as housewife and also more determinants such as educational attainment of the household head, relation to the migrant, investment in business and loan repayment. The other categories of employment status show the significant relationship with the age of migrant, household land and living expenses at the origin. The study suggests that the employment status of the household head has strong correlation with socio-economic as well as socio-demographic characteristics in the remittance behaviour of Bangladeshi households. Thus, highlight the importance of differentiating with respect to employment status of the household head when analysing the determinants of remittances.

Keywords: remittance; employment status; household head; rural household.

JEL Classifications: A12; B21; C51; C81; D19; J19; R23.

1. Introduction

According to the International Organization for Migration (IOM), there are an accounted 191 million global migrants in 2005, up from 176 million in 2000. Migrants include 3.0 per cent of the worldwide population. For the period 2000-10, the world migrant stock increased double as fast than during the last decade. In 1990s, the global migrant stock increased at an average of about 2 million migrants per year. During the period 2000-10, the outgrowth in the migrant stock accelerated to about 4.6 million migrants annually. There are 232 million international migrants are staying in the world today. Since 1990, the number of international migrants in the global North grew by about 53 million (65%), on the other hand the migrant population in the global South increased by about 24 million (34%). Nowadays, around six out of every ten international migrants stay in the developed nations (UN, 2013).

In 2006, remittance flows are accounted to have go beyond USD 276 billion globally, USD 206 billion of which sent to developing countries. According to World Bank database (2014), the global remittance flow, which has touched \$550 billion last year, is expected to grow by 8 per cent per annum in the next few of years. Of the total remittance fund, \$414 billion were received by developing countries, especially Bangladesh, China, India, Mexico, the Philippines, and Pakistan.

Bangladeshi migrants in Italy are predominantly single and male migrants who are living under 'transnationally split' (Yeoh et al., 2002) conditions

and obligated to maintain economic and social relations with their family members back home (Rahman and Kabir, 2012). The obligation of maintaining sustained economic and social ties with home stems from the dominance of the household in the social and economic affairs of the Bangladeshi society and their transnational household members. Individual migrant is deeply enmeshed in a complex web of household relations and dependencies: He/she moves internationally for work as an envoy of the extended household that places the well-being of the extended family above the individual migrant's interests (Rahman, 2011). Whether it is temporary labour migration such as migration to the Middle East or more permanent form of migration such as migration to Italy, maintaining sustained economic relations with left behind households remain one of the key priorities for migrant members (Ullah, 2010; Rahman, 2009). This is comprehensive evidenced in the annual inflow of remittances to Bangladesh, which has increased from around \$4.2 billion in 2005 to nearly \$10.9 billion in 2013 (BMET, 2014).

These facts and figures indicate that international migration and remittance is an intricate phenomenon, the dynamics of which are increasingly turning a drastic policy topic global economic, social, legal and cultural topic.

2. Theoretical framework

Research and empirical findings on the determinants of international remittances in Bangladesh is limited by the remittance processes and data discrepancies. Different theories explicate different outcomes of the

remittances. Among the factors, household structure (e.g., household size, male-female ratio), income sources, marital status, gender of household head, time abroad, etc. play influential roles in determining the amount and use of the remittances in the household.

The New Economics of Labour Migration (NELM) characterises migration as a household decision determined by the specific household characteristics (Stark and Bloom, 1985). Therefore, the issue of remittances and their determinants has become a key consideration in a number of theoretical and empirical studies. A distinguishing attribute of the NELM model is its simultaneous consideration of migration determinants, remittance behaviour and impacts making NELM models relatively demanding in estimation methods and data requirements. Another key insight of NELM is that households allocate members to improve not only absolute but relative income and alleviate their deprivation against a reference group like the village community (Stark and Bloom 1985; Stark, Taylor and Yitzhaki, 1986; Stark and Taylor, 1989; Stark, 1991).

Micro-level studies of remittances are either based on household surveys that include remittance-receiving households (Gubert, 2002) or specific surveys of the migrants in the originating or destination country (Amuedo-Dorantes and Pozo, 2006; Holst and Schrooten, 2006). Against such a theoretical framework, a broad stream of studies has pioneered the determinants of remittances and their socio-economic impact on countries, communities and households that have sent workers abroad (Borja 2012). Two broad perspectives have been adopted: macro determinants and impact of foreign remittances on originating countries and their micro determinants and consequences. The approach adopted in this study will be on the latter as the study area is the Shariatpur District of Bangladesh which has traditionally sent migrant workers to Italy for a considerable time.

3. Literature review

The literatures on remittances and employment status of the household head have so far explored mostly on the impact on the remitting patterns of migrants at the origin. Early 1980s, a few studies, using mostly internal remittances data, indicate that marital status does influence remitting behaviour (Lucas and Stark, 1985; Kaufmann and Lindauer, 1986). The household head employment status play vital role in remittance behaviour (Quartey, 2006), there are few sectorial differences, for instance, the household head employment in public sector, private formal sector, export farmer, crop farmer, private, informal and unemployment play different impacts. In the 1990s also supported this idea, but these studies have also

been able to construct a story of why we may observe these differences among the occupational level of household head.

According to Osili (2007) migrant age is one of the important determinant influencing remittance behaviour. There is a relationship between age of the migrants and the length of stay at the destination (Mejivar et al., 1998; Rodriguez, 1996), often increase income and therefore also the available pool for remittance. Higher levels of remittances are sent by individuals under younger of age compared to older migrants (de la Briere et al., 1997). Likely one of the greatest determinant outcomes of the migrant age has to do with the migrant's specific period in the household life cycle. However, Lerch et al (2006) find the relationship between the age of migrant and the likelihood to send the money to the destination and the length of stay additionally correlates with the age of migrants also find the linkage with different stages of age with the kinship of family relationship which influences remit to the household at the origin. The age of household head factor vary from country to country (DeVoretz and Vadean, 2008), gender behaviour in the remittance motive, for example male household less like to receive remittance rather than female (McDonald and Valenzuela, 2012), the older household head receive more remittance than the younger household head which reveal that the adult children care for their old parents as well their grant parents (Germenji et al 2001).

Using data from the Dominican Sierra (de la Brière, Sadoulet, de Janvry and Lambert 2002), find that there are structural differences in remittance behaviour across gender, reflected in the significance of the interaction terms of gender with other determinants of remittances. However, Agarwal and Horowitz (2002), using data from Guyana, find that gender matters for the amount remitted (males remit a higher amount), but not for the likelihood of remitting. Moreover, Sana and Massey (2005) find that in the Dominican Republic, daughters living abroad are stronger predictors of remittances than sons living abroad. The inverse is true for Mexico, while sons living abroad are stronger predictors of remittances than daughters living abroad. Moreover, Blue (2004) found that female Cuban migrants are more reliable remitters than male Cuban migrants. Furthermore, Naufal (2008) finds that female migrants behave more altruistically than their male counterparts.

Several studies show that migrant marital status and residency pattern of household members, including spouses and children, are significant determinants of remittance motivation (Johnson and Whitelaw 1974; Menjivar et al. 1998; Vanwey 2004; Casale and Posel,

2006; Luke, 2007; Alba and Sugi 2009). According to Sahu and Das (2009) single migrants and married heads living alone at the destination are likely to remit more than married heads living with their spouse and children. However Collier et al (2011) find that migrants' marital status does not influence the decision to remittance motivation. Furthermore, (Sorenson, 2004a, 2004b, 2005; Atekmangoh, 2011) reveal that marital status is a key determinant for remittance behaviour and it also vary with gender discrimination when migrant change their marital status after migration, therefore remittance receiving household also change at the origin (Piper, 2005). Moreover, remittances increase while household head becomes a grandparent or the spouse lives outside or divorced, the household head send monies to share with the number of nuclear household members living outside the household (DeVoretz and Vadean, 2007).

In the micro-economic level studies of the determinants of remittances show the length of stay of the migrants different effects, some studies that consider the duration of migration as a single independent variable and find negative impacts (Menjivar et al, 1998; Fairchild and Simpson, 2004; Holst and Schrooten, 2006; Vargas-Silva, 2006;), while others find that the length of stay no significant (Merkle and Zimmermann, 1992). However, (Simati and Gibson, 2001; Brown, 1998, 1997) find that remittance tends to increase with the time of stay of migrants in the country of destination. There also few evidence show that the effect of the duration of migration in the destination country on remittance motivation ambiguous (Banarjee, 1984;) and others show that the remittances flow increase initial stage of migration but decrease over time (Lucas and Stark, 1985; Banarjee, 1984; Vete, 1995).

Many empirical studies explore that the number of trips to the household members influence remittance behaviour (Lerch et al., 2006) Number of trips and remittance motivation. Many empirical studies explore that the number of trips to the household members influence remittance behaviour (Lerch et al., 2006; Garip-2012; Roberts and Morris, 2003). During the visit at the origin, migrant bring gifts for their household members, family, extended and fictive kin, and friends, they assert and keep up their community networks (Goldring, 1998) therefore the remittance effect direct and indirect at the home country in cash and kind. In contrast, rarely trip to the household members a lower likelihood to send remittances either cash or kind, at the same time, there is a gender and origin discrimination as (Lerch et al., 2006).

Migrant who make frequent visits at the origin, not only to sustain community liaison, but also to lead or to constitute critical economic linkages (Kemper,

1981). On the other hand Holst and Schrooten (2006) find that the personal trips to the origin country has no significant impact neither the probability of remittance motive or the amount of remittances, furthermore the migrants are not a homogenous group with consideration to their remittance motivation. However, Grabel (2008) finds that the huge percentages of remittances are hand carry by migrants during the trips at the home (Garip-2012; Roberts and Morris, 2003). During the visit at the origin, migrant bring gifts for their household members, family, extended and fictive kin, and friends, they assert and keep up their community membership (Goldring, 1998) therefore the remittance effect direct and indirect at the home country in cash and kind. In contrast, rarely trip to the household members a lower likelihood to send remittances either cash or kind, at the same time, there is a gender and origin discrimination as (Lerch et al., 2006). Migrant who make frequent visits at the origin, not only to sustain community liaison, but also to lead or to constitute critical economic linkages (Kemper, 1981). On the other hand Holst and Schrooten (2006) find that the personal trips to the origin country has no significant impact neither the probability of remittance motive or the amount of remittances, furthermore the migrants are not a homogenous group with consideration to their remittance motivation.

Age of the household head is one of important determinant which play vital role in the remittance behaviour and the age factor also vary from country to country (DeVoretz and Vadean, 2008). Age of the household head nexus with gender behaviour in the remittance motive, for example male household less like to receive remittance rather than female (McDonald and Valenzuela, 2012). However, Germejni et al (2001) show the older household head receive more remittance than the younger household head which reveal that the adult children care for their old parents as well their grant parents. Moreover, Walewski, (2009) shows reverse outcomes that the younger household head tend to receive remittance more and subsequently decrease and strong correlation with the household head age and remittance flow.

Gender of the household head special attention (Karakaplan et al, 2012) as the male-headed households remittance motivation and use differently from female headed which affect households resource allocation (Pfeiffer et al., 2008). As for, who left behind their wife at the origin, the women at the household experience changes and increase greater responsibilities to the household budget and remittance income as well children education.

Marital Status of Household Head

Marital status of the households head one of the key demographic characteristic influence to receive

remittances. Empirical study shows that the households with married head tend to receive comparatively lower remittances across the year, whereas remittances flow to widow and otherwise not married relatively higher, however the female-headed households receive more remittance specially those who are married (Pfau, 2008).

Education of Households Head

Higher education levels of the household head may reflect better household resources and income opportunities and so less economic need from overseas income, therefore the educational attainment of the household head not significant with remittance amount and such provide some support the altruism motive (McDonald and Valenzuela, 2012).

The empirical studies on international migrant and remittances show that a nexus among religiosity and pro-social, behaviours of the migrants and their households members (Cadge and Ecklund, 2007; Ecklund, 2006) and also political (Gruber et al., 2008) and better health outcomes (Ellison, 1991). Few empirical studies show a relationship between religiosity and positive social behaviour (Ellison 1991, Cadge and Ecklund, 2007; Cadge, 2006) and also nexus to remittance behaviour, for instance those who attend religious service regularly, more likely remit than irregular or non-regular attenders (Cadge and Ecklund, 2007). Kelly and Solomon (2009) explore that religion and the practices of religious activities relates to the altruistic motive of remittance behaviour.

Household size is one of the factors of migration as well as remittance behaviour. The empirical study Atamanov and Berg (2012) show larger household size tends to be migration more than small size of households. Sackey (2010) finds household size statistically significant with the exchange and insurance motive to remit to their home country. Mishra (2011) also explores that household size affect the remittances inflows in Nepal. Ullah (2007) shows that average migrant member household size in Bangladesh six including migrant member.

The households head occupation and employment status linkage with migration decision and remittance motivation as well of the household migrant member. According to Quartey (2006), there are few sectoral differences, for instance, the household head employment in public sector, private formal sector, export farmer, crop farmer, private, informal and unemployment play different impacts. Thus, this study dare to take consideration to delve out the nexus between the employment status of the household head at the origin and other socio-demographic characteristics of individual migrant, household member and household composition.

4. Methodology

This study chose a quantitative method approach as its methodology to accommodate method for an extensive solution of the research problem and answer the research questions.

4.1 Selection of survey village and course of the survey

In line with the study focus, the selection of the study area in Bangladesh was based on the high incidence of household members migrating to Italy at the sub-district level (Upazila) and the prevalence of remittance-receiving households at the sub-sub-district level (Union Parisad). Shariatpur is located in the Dhaka division and in the greater Faridpur District. Among the households, a significant number of migrants are from Naria Upazila, Shariatpur District. Naria sub-district has 14 sub-sub-districts and Vogeshore union one of the sub-sub-districts, has been selected randomly for census data because there is no available published data on Bangladeshi migrant workers in Italy. Emigration from Bangladesh to Italy is predominantly a rural phenomenon. Therefore, the fieldwork undertaken for this research consists of an ethnographic village study in Bangladesh with particular reference to remittance sending migrant worker in Italy to bridge the micro and macro paradigms of migration and remittance, and offer analytical insights into the determinants and impacts of such remittance.

4.2 Study Design

The primary data was collected from households in the Naria Upazila of Shariatpur District in Bangladesh as the researcher is from this area and is familiar with its geography and people. In the second phase, first-hand knowledge was obtained through ask a single question (whether the household has members who have worked in Italy or not) to each of the 4013 households in the 10 study villages. Thereafter a structured questionnaire in which several open ended and closed ended questions were asked to exactly identify different factors playing a pivotal role for migrants' families. The responses were collected in a quantitative way, i.e. through an appropriate questionnaire, and through a qualitative method, through conducting direct interviews. The respondents were the heads of households or senior members of families which had a member. Their responses were analysed and summarised to derive conclusions about the migration impacts, by post-and pre migration data.

4.3 Sample Size

In selecting a representative sample of the population, Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) recommendation was accepted in this study. After categorising the household migrant members in Italy a random sample of 300 households was selected, the share in each village corresponding to their proportion in the whole population (the remittance received household). Then, the remittance received households in each village were picked randomly. In the process, every household was coded during the first stage census survey and recorded on a separate identical size of piece of paper. Thereafter, all folded papers were thoroughly mixed up to assure the same probability of selection of each household and to overcome systematic sampling error. One folded paper was picked up each time by the researcher himself. After each selection, the pile of folder papers was mixed up again and another person was chosen only to pick up another folded paper and the process continued until the sample remittance received household total was attained. Finally the interviews of selected households were administered with structured and semi-structured questionnaires.

4.4 Ethical Issues

This research was conducted in compliance with the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007) and was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of Southern Cross University (Approval Number ECN-13-141).

5. Results

5.1 Frequency of Remittance

The respondents were asked about the remittances received frequencies who remittance from Italy of their household migrant member. Table 1.1 explores that the remittances received frequencies; the majority 57.0% were sent bimonthly basis remittance to their left behind household members. The others were sent 22% at any necessary, 20% monthly and 1% only festivals. The 3% household were received the maximum level of remittances range BDT 14,00,001 to 15,00,000.

Table 1.1: Cross Tabulation Household yearly remittance received and Frequency of Remittance

Household yearly remittance received (BDT)	Frequency of Remittance				Total
	Monthly	Bimonthly	At any necessary	Festivals	
100,001-200,000	0	0	33	3	36
200,001-300,000	6	18	12	0	36
300,001-400,000	0	3	15	0	18
400,001-500,000	0	15	3	0	18
500,001-600,000	0	66	0	0	66
600,001-700,000	3	42	3	0	48
700,001-800,000	24	21	0	0	45
800,001-900,000	0	3	0	0	3
900,001-1000,000	6	3	0	0	9
1100,001-1200,000	15	0	0	0	15
1300,001-1400,000	3	0	0	0	3
1400,001-1500,000	3	0	0	0	3
Total	60	171	66	3	300
% of Total	20.0%	57.0%	22.0%	1.0%	100.0%

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

However, the following figure (1.1) shows that the bimonthly remittances received household were received different ranges of remittances. Among the ranges, the highest percentage of household 39% were received yearly BDT 500,001-600,000. However, their highest level of remittances BDT 9,00,001-10,00,000 of 2% and lowest level of remittances BDT 2,00,001-3,00,000 of 10%.

Figure 1.1: Distribution of bio monthly remittances received frequency

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

5.2 Employment status and remittances

The respondents were asked about the employment status of household head who were received remittance from Italy of their household migrant member. Table 1.2 explores that 47% household head employment status were housewife, 40% businessman, 6% farmer, 4% retired person and 3% private service. The data reveal most of the household head employment status housewife and their maximum yearly remittance receiving flows between BDT 1400,000 to 1500,000.

Table 1.2: Cross Tabulation Household yearly remittance received and employment of household head

Household yearly remittance received (BDT)	Employment Status of Household Head					Total
	Retired	House wife	Farmer	Private Service	Businessman	
1,00,001-2,00,000	6	12	0	3	15	36
2,00,001-3,00,000	0	21	0	3	12	36
3,00,001-4,00,000	0	9	0	0	9	18
4,00,001-5,00,000	0	12	0	3	3	18
5,00,001-6,00,000	6	27	12	0	21	66
6,00,001-7,00,000	0	15	0	0	33	48
7,00,001-800,000	0	18	0	0	27	45
8,00,001-900,000	0	0	3	0	0	3
9,00,001-10,00,000	0	6	3	0	0	9
11,00,001-12,00,000	0	15	0	0	0	15
13,00,001-14,00,000	0	3	0	0	0	3
14,00,001-15,00,000	0	3	0	0	0	3
Total	12	141	18	9	120	300
% of Total	4.0%	47.0%	6.0%	3.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

Furthermore, the following figure (1.2) shows that the housewife employment statuses of household head were received different ranges of remittances. Among the ranges, the highest percentage of household head 19% were received yearly BDT 500,001-600,000. However, their highest level of remittances BDT 14,00,001-15,00,000 of 2% and lowest level of remittances BDT 1,00,001-2,00,000 of 8%.

Figure 1.2: Distribution of Housewife remittance receiving household head

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

5.3 Remittance determinants of the rural households

The long and short regression allows the assessment of the direction and strength of causality existing between the dependent and independent variables. The best fit model has statistically been developed, both (short and long) regression models are applied in the data analysis because whole sample has been broken into sub-samples with specific attributes (e.g., marital status of migrant, employment status of household head, household relation to migrant, gender of household head, etc) to generate a clear picture about the factors influencing the remittances of those specific study households. Therefore, the regressions are:

$$RmY = \alpha + \alpha_1 AGE_m + \alpha_2 EDU_m + \alpha_3 MARSm + \alpha_4 YMIG_m + \alpha_5 LEGS_m + \alpha_6 NVIST_m + \alpha_7 AGE_{hh} + \alpha_8 GEN_{hh} + \alpha_9 MARShh + \alpha_{10} EDU_{hh} + \alpha_{11} REL_{hh} + \alpha_{12} EMPS_{hh} + \alpha_{13} RELM_{hh} + \alpha_{14} HHsize + \alpha_{15} HLOWtitle + \alpha_{16} Invest_Fin_Sec + \alpha_{17} Invest_Hous_Dev + \alpha_{18} Ln_Live_Exp + \alpha_{19} Ln_HH_Incom + \alpha_{20} Inest_Busi + \alpha_{21} Ln_Welf + \alpha_{23} Loan_Rep + e^1 \text{-----}(1.1: \text{Long regression}) \text{ and}$$

$$RmY = \alpha + \alpha_1 AGE_m + \alpha_2 MARSm + \alpha_3 NVIST_m + \alpha_4 AGE_{hh} + \alpha_5 GEN_{hh} + \alpha_6 MARShh + \alpha_7 EMPS_{hh} + \alpha_8 RELM_{hh} + \alpha_9 Invest_Hous_Sec + \alpha_{10} Ln_Land + \alpha_{11} Ln_Live_Exp + \pi_1 \text{.....}(1.2)$$

The identification of all these variables are given in Appendix Table-I with the exception of the error terms e_1 and π_1 which satisfy the assumptions of-

- (i) zero mean, $E(e_1)=0$; $E(\pi_1)=0$
- (ii) constant variance, $E(e_1)^2=\partial e^2$; $E(\pi_1)^2=\partial \pi^2$
- (iii) no autocorrelation exist in the error e_1 and π_1 ; $E(e_{1i})=0$ and $E(\pi_{1j})=0$; where $1 \neq j$

5.4 The empirical results

The cross sectional data collected from 300 households through a one-off primary survey are used to estimate the two regression models. To identify the variation in the strength of the remittance determinants, expected relationships between the dependent and independent variables and quantify those relationships with the maximum information, the analysis comprises following two parts:

- (a) Analysis of the whole sample in the 10 villages;
- (b) Unit analysis of household according to the employment status of household head

The results of these analyses are reported following:

5.5 The whole sample

The results of the whole sample consisting of 300 households show the explanatory power of both long and short regressions measured by adjusted R^2 values which are statistically significant and high. Table 4.26 indicates that R^2 values for long and short regression equations are about 0.565 and 0.634 respectively. The test results of overall significance, F-test, are also statistically highly significant at the level of 1% in both regression equations. Table 1.3 shows that eleven variables are statistically insignificant in the long regression whereas the range of significance levels of the rest of eleven variables varies between 1% to 5% level in both regressions. Except for marital status of migrant (MARSm) and Log Land (Ln_Land) have been removed at the second stage of the model, due to statistically insignificant.

Table 1.3: Determinants of average household remittance: Log linear regression results of the 10 rural villages, 2013

Model	Dependent variable					
	Household yearly remittance received (RmY)					
	Long regression			Short regression		
	Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Coefficients	t-value	p-value
AGEm	-.498	-3.341	.001	-.473	-4.718	.000
EDUm	.049	.297	.767			
MARSm	-.820	-2.424	.016	-.470	-1.692	.092
YMIgM	.035	.115	.909			
LEGSm	-.084	-.153	.878	.518	9.559	.000
NVISTm	.398	4.239	.000			
AGEhh	.417	4.113	.000	.400	4.993	.000
GENhh	2.427	2.988	.003	3.542	7.556	.000
MARShh	3.798	4.899	.000	2.686	5.639	.000
EDUhh	.101	.779	.437			
RELhh	.502	1.016	.311			
EMPShh	-.299	-3.222	.001	-.039	-1.681	.094
RELMhh	.601	2.763	.006	.615	3.896	.000
HHsize	.018	.205	.838			
HLOWNtitle	.044	.186	.853			
Invest_Fin_Sec	.266	1.683	.094			
Invest_Hous_Dev	2.021	4.632	.000	1.668	5.890	.000
Ln_Land	.342	1.757	.080	.180	1.857	.064
Ln_Live_Exp	2.693	3.511	.001	1.779	5.151	.000
Ln_HH_Incom	-.193	-.643	.521			
Invest_Busi	.243	2.535	.012			
Ln_WelF	.534	.829	.408			
Loan_Rep	-.810	-1.680	.095			
Intercept			-46.141			-31.763
R ²			.611			.648
Adjusted R ²			.565			.634
F-statistic			13.294			48.146
Sum squared residual			536.164			832.331
Durbin-Watson statistics (d)			1.891			2.049
Observation			300			300

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

5.6 Unit Analysis of the employment status of household head

Table 1.4 explored the employment status of household head as a housewife. The full regression model showed (at the long regressions equation) the significance level at .001 while other model .094 level of confidence. The result showed that the contradictory relationship between the housewife of the household head and remittances inflows. The study intended to delve out the different employment status with other variables. Hence, the sample broken into different sub-samples as follows:

5.6.1 The Housewife of the household head

Due to statistical limitation, the long regression could not run into SPSS at the housewife of the household head while short regression result table 1.4 showed that the strong significance with other variable such AGEm MARSm, NVISTm, AGEhh, Invest_Hous_Dev and Ln_Live_Exp.

Table 1.4: Determinants of average household remittance: Short-Log linear regression results housewife household head in the 10 rural villages, 2013

Determinants	Dependent variable		
	Household yearly remittance received (RmY)		
	Short regression		
	Coefficients	t-value	p-value
AGEm	-.383	-2.559	.012
MARSm	2.871	4.803	.000
NVISTm	.560	10.103	.000
AGEhh	.333	2.122	.036
MARShh	.140	.154	.878
RELMhh	1.467	.986	.326
Invest_Hous_Dev	1.596	5.469	.000
Ln_Land	-.300	-2.033	.044
Ln_Live_Exp	3.156	7.205	.000
R ²			.840
Adjusted R ²			.829
F-statistic			76.198
Sum squared residual			248.133
Durbin-Watson statistics (d)			2.297
Observation			141

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

5.6.2 The household head as a Businessman

The household head as a businessman explored (Table 1.5) different significant relationship among the other determinants of remittances. Such as, at the long regressions result showed the strong relationship with AGEm, NVISTm AGEhh, EDUhh Ln_Live_Exp, Inest_Busi and Loan_Rep. While short regressions revealed that the strong significance with AGEm, NVISTm AGEhh, RELMhh and Invest_Hous_Dev.

Table 1.5: Log linear regression results of businessman household head in the 10 rural villages, 2013

Determinants	Dependent variable					
	Household yearly remittance received (RmY)					
	Long regression			Short regression		
	Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Coefficients	t-value	p-value
AGEm	-.634	-4.418	.000	-.879	-6.520	.000
EDUm	.332	1.933	.056			
MARSm	-.351	-1.132	.260	-.629	-1.749	.083
YMIgM	-.495	-1.558	.122			
LEGSm	1.655	1.802	.075			
NVISTm	.418	3.410	.001	.406	3.611	.000
AGEhh	.264	2.972	.004	.299	2.933	.004
EDUhh	.747	4.579	.000			
RELhh	.099	.202	.840			
RELMhh	.233	1.106	.272	.703	4.264	.000
HHsize	.135	1.023	.309			
HLOWNtitle	.242	.831	.408			
Invest_Fin_Sec	.183	1.289	.200			
Invest_Hous_Dev	.833	1.449	.151	2.796	5.923	.000
Ln_Land	.058	.257	.798	.103	.711	.479
Ln_Live_Exp	2.479	3.253	.002	1.192	1.925	.057
Ln_HH_Incom	-.536	-1.463	.147			
Invest_Busi	.303	3.894	.000			
Ln_WelF	-1.341	-1.566	.121			
Loan_Rep	3.136	3.977	.000			
R ²			.750			.555
Adjusted R ²			.700			.523
F-statistic			14.859			17.317
Sum squared residual			130.066			231.529
Durbin-Watson statistics (d)			2.025			1.774
Observation			120			120

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

5.6.3 The household as Otherwise: Retired, Farmer and Private Service

In addition, the unit analysis of the employment status of the household head as otherwise likely retired, farmer and private service showed (table 1.6) at the short regressions that the strong significance relationship with AGEm, Ln_Land and Ln_Live_Exp. In this unit also did not run regressions due to statistical limitation.

Table 1.6: Determinants of average household remittance: Short-Log linear regression results otherwise household head in the 10 rural villages, 2013

Determinants	Dependent variable		
	Household yearly remittance received (RmY)		
	Short regression		
	Coefficients	t-value	p-value
AGEm	-1.357	-5.474	.000
MARSm	.838	1.778	.085
NVISTm	-.941	-2.928	.006
AGEhh	.271	1.719	.096
EMPShh	-.653	-6.489	.000
Invest_Hous_Dev	-.160	-.244	.809
Ln_Land	3.503	9.785	.000
Ln_Live_Exp	5.152	8.009	.000
R ²			.935
Adjusted R ²			.918
F-statistic			54.154
Sum squared residual			14.915
Durbin-Watson statistics (d)			2.524
Observation			39

6. Conclusions

Unique result from the previous literature, which mostly focuses on either in general on the household members employment status. This study finds also analyse overall significance level of all other determinants of remittances. However, this research delves out more on the specific group of household head. This unit analysis allows us to test the significance level of different group household head employment status and their relationship with other key determinants of remittances at the household level at the rural micro economy.

The empirical findings suggest that the employment status of the household head is one of the determinants of remittances. In addition, the employment status of the household head also has different occupations of different influential factors such as the most common variable age of migrant is strongly associates with all the types of employment status of the household head although level of significance has slightly discrimination. The age of migrant also indicate us the kinship relationship with household members.

Overall, the findings suggests that the differences of the relationship among the other determinants of three (housewife, businessman and other) employment status of the household head. As for housewife is mostly associates with the age of migrant, marital status of the migrant, number of visit by the migrant, age of household head, investment in housing development and household living expenses. While businessman is closely related with all variables as housewife and also more determinants such as educational attainment of the household head, relation to the migrant, investment in business and loan repayment. The other categories of employment status show the significant relationship with the age of migrant, household land and living expenses at the origin.

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Appendix-I

Specification of variables for multivariate analysis

Group of variables	Name of variables	Identification
Dependent Variable		
Annual household remittance received	RmY	Natural log of yearly remittance, numeric (BDT)
Independent variable		
Individual characteristics (migrant and household head)	Age of migrant (AGEm)	Numeric (year)
	Education of Migrant (EDUm)	Numeric (coding)
	Marital Status of Migrant (MARSm)	Numeric (coding)
	Year of Migration (YMIGm)	Numeric (year)
	Legal Status of Migrant (LEGSm)	Numeric (coding)
	Number of Visit by Migrant (NVISTm)	Numeric
	Age of Household Head (AGEhh)	Numeric (year)
	Gender of Household Head (GENhh)	Numeric (coding)
	Marital Status of Household (Head MARShh)	Numeric (coding)
	Education Level of Household Head (EDUhh)	Numeric (coding)
	Religion of Household Head (RELhh)	Numeric (coding)
	Employment Status of Household Head (EMPShh)	Numeric (coding)
	Household Head Relation to Migrant (RELMhh)	Numeric (coding)
	Household Characteristics	Household Size (HHsize)
Household Land Ownership (HLOWtitle)		Numeric (coding)
Investment in Financial Sectors (Invest_Fin_Sec)		Numeric (coding)
Investment in House Development (Invest_Hous_Dev)		Numeric (coding)
Log of Household Living Expenditure (Ln_Live_Exp)		Natural log of HH yearly living expenditure, numeric (BDT)
Log of Household Yearly Income (Ln_HH_Incom)		Natural log of yearly income except remittance, numeric (BDT)
Investment in Business (Inest_Busi)		Numeric
Log of Household Welfare Expenses (Ln_Welf)		Natural log of yearly HH welfare expenses, numeric (BDT)
Loan Repayment (Loan_Rep)	Numeric (coding)	

Source: Author developed for this study